

Mahabaleshwar Sail's *Age of Franzy*: Recounting a Forgotten the History of Goa

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Abstract: This paper highlights Mahabaleshwar Sail's *Age of Frenzy*'s true story of Goa state. *Age of Frenzy* originally written in Konkani language, then it has translated into English. Sail depicts the true story of Goa state especially destroys of Konkani culture and conversation into Christianity. We don't not find true social history in colonial history but in literature we find true socio-cultural history of India.

Key Words: goa, Konkani, sail, church

Age of Frenzy is a Konkani novel by Mahabaleshwar Sail. Vidya Pai has translated it into English. Mahabaleshwar Sail was born on 4th August 1943, at Shejebag, Majali, a small village of Uttara Kannada district of Karnataka state. He was born into a family of agriculturalists. Sail's father was in the Army, and due to his father's demise, Sail had to leave school during his childhood and engage in agriculture. He started school at the age of six and dropped out in the eighth standard. Subsequently, he enrolled himself in the Indian Army. Sail also participated in the Indo-Pakistani War of 1965 and was stationed at the Hussainiwala border. He also served as a United Nations peacekeeper between 1964–1965 at the border between Israel and Egypt. Sail worked as a supervisor in the Forest Department, he was also in Goa, Daman, and Diu Police. Sail worked in India Post till his retirement. Sail initially wrote in the Marathi language but later started writing in the Konkani language too. His first story appeared in Pralhad Keshav Atre's Saptahik Navyug weekly, the first story he wrote during a lull in the battle after the Tashkent Declaration. Sail has written stories, novels and children's literature in the Konkani language. He has authored novels, stories and plays in the Marathi language. His first Konkani novel was *Kaali Ganga* in 1996. It dealt with the lives of the farming communities on the banks of the Kali River (Karnataka) in Karwar. Sail received the Sahitya Akadami Award in Konkani language for his short story collection *Taranga* in 1993. Sail's writing is characterised by research on the topic and the use of Konkani language words from Karwar region. His novels are characterized by the use of strong female heroines and an excellent depiction of the characters. Sail's *Yug Sanvar* in Konkani language and *Taanda* in the Marathi language are based on the Goa Inquisition in 1510. The Portuguese arrived in Goa armed with guns, swords, and crucifixes to the agricultural village of Adolshi, where Hindus have been living peacefully. A sense of foreboding fills them as the tiger prowls, cow bones appear in wells, and chariot wheels break on festival day. The Portuguese king has licensed Jesuits to take over and staunch white men move about preaching the word of the Son of God. The land is seized, and families are broken. But Padre Simao Peres is convinced that love and not force will bring about a change of heart. With the Inquisition looming like an axe over everyone's heads, a saga of choice plays out for the people of the village. Mahabaleshwar Sail's epic novel, *Age of Frenzy*,

documents a turbulent past of religious rifts, caste hierarchies and power shifts which changed the ethos of a significant part of the western coastline of India forever.

The novel begins with a description of the Hindu culture of Goa. Saanton Nayak is a farmer; he led his pair of bullocks and set up the plough in his field at Khargali. He shouted at the bullocks and the plough moved forward, they had barely gone up and down twice when the plough's wooden peg came loose and it wobbled crookedly. Suddenly a tiger jumped on bullocks, killed them and disappeared in the forest. Villagers discussed not performing of the rituals properly, they feel that is the reason to kill the bullocks. The Nayak community failed to perform the puja every Monday at Shivaddo. If they performed a puja the Lord will save the village. Venku Nayak's family had been elected to perform the rituals and conduct all the festivals on behalf of the Nayak community. They have to perform the puja at the little shrine of the guardian spirit of the village and worship the village deity Lord Ramnath. Venku Nayak worshiped the Barmo shrine, he poured some oil into the stone lamps that stood before each deity and set them alight. Mhablu Nayak asked, "Venku bhau, did you ask this deity why all this happening?" Our calves get struck in the mud; small coconuts fall from the trees. Tigers kill out bullocks even as they stand yoked to the plough. Is there something wrong with the way you worship the deities? or have the gods withdraw their benevolence and protection" (Sail 4). Mhablu Nayak questioned, "If they don't protect the village what use are these gods to us? Why should we worship them or place balls of sweet beaten rice on their heads?" (Sail 4). There was a big discussion in between Mhablu and Venku bhau. He is helpless, he said, "Who am I to demand an answer from the gods? I am only doing my job of performing the rituals every week" (Sail 4). There was a practice of untouchables in the village of Goa, there was a restriction in the village that, "A man who belongs to another faith cannot spend a night in this village" (Sail 8). Things have changed a lot in the village.

Age of Frenzy depicts the arrival of the Portuguese in Goa. The white-skinned people came to Goa, the white-skinned devils have entered the village and they killed a huge wild boar up in the hills. Lingu Nayak and Gana Nayak were working in the field, they saw white-skinned people. They discussed their nature. Gana whispered, "they eat the flesh and cows and drink human blood.' 'A race of red demons. Their nails and teeth must be sharp, like pointed stakes. Their guns have fire inside the spark goes right through a man and kills him'. "He died immediately, or he dies later when his body begins to rot. They smear snake poison on their swords, I have heard" (Sail 9). Captain Castel Figredi had come along with some soldiers and they drank water in the temple tank. Captain Castel Figredi heard that, "the Brahmins were the real decision-makers in the Goa society" (Sail 10). Brahmins were an intelligent class, who could read and write. Captain came to the village and said, "I am the captain in charge of this region. We have defeated Adil Shah and snatched Goa from him. You are now King of Portugal's subjects" (Sail 11). Captain called the villagers and declared, they are the rulers of Goa, he said, "We have come here today to get an assurance that you have accepted the king of Portugal as your sovereign. All the revenues and taxes will have to be deposited with us from now on" (Sail 12). He called Kulkarni and Gaonkar order them to use Cruzado currency. Bhavani Shenai is a hot-headed young man, he opposed and shouted, "You are an impure race come from across the sea. We have nothing to do with your King; we will not offer solutations to him or to any of you. Our heads will only how before our gods" (Sail 15). Captian grabbed his button and blow on him, he fell on the ground. They entered Ravalnath temple with boots and defiled the temple. The white-skinned people killed a huge boar in

the hills and distributed its meat to everyone. Figradi speaks of national culture, “Some of these people eat only fruits and vegetables others eat meat” (Sail 49). He knows that Indian society is caste based.

Age of Frenzy depicts the history of conversion. Adolshi was a small village about sixteen miles from Goapattana. There was fearful atmosphere in Goa, a bad new has been spread around the village that the foreigners had barged into Kalpur and Merces with their new religion. Rumours were spreading that, “Those people fed the villagers cow meat says it was deer meat. The unfortunate ones who ate it become outcastes” (Sail 20). Outcaste people were forcibly converted to Christianity. All the thieves in Goa’s jails had been converted to Christianity and were set free. Padre Simao Peres come to village and visited every settlement and delivered a lecture. He spoke reverently of the greatness of Jesus Christ. Padre Simao started his Sermon, “Jesus, Son of God, born of the holy Virgin Mary come to this world to spread compassion and bring happiness and joy. His heart overflowed with love and compassion. He said to love your family, love your neighbors and most importantly, love your enemies too”. “Forgive your enemy for what evil he has done to you and he will become your dearest friend” (Sail 121-22). Padre Simao also said, “Accept Jesus as your Lord, believe in Him. Tell Him all your sorrow and your troubles will vanish” (Sail 22). Annu accepted the religion, Guna opposes the conversion, and he angrily spoke, “We hear that your people are converting men forcibly in Goapattana and other villages that the Chamundeshwara temple on Chormen Island has been destroyed” (Sail 23). Annu converted to Christianity, he met soldier Demu, and he converted to Christianity. Demu narrates the process of conversion, “Nothing much. You bathe in a lake so that your past is washed away. Then they smear oil on your temples and give you something to eat. Don’t ask what is, just swallow it. Then, they celebrate Mass and give you a Christen name” (Sali 26). Padre Simao was very active; he stayed in Adolshi village and learned Konkani language. He was preaching Jesus’s significance and baptized untouchables. He was dreaming that he wants to convert every one of the villages to Christianity. There was a practice of untouchability in the village; when Padri touched Biru Nayaka. He thrashed him then went home and gets bathed and sprinkled dung water on himself.

Age of Frenzy depicts the caste system, practice of untouchability, caste hierarchy and Sati system in Indian society. Padre Simao and Annu approached the astrologer’s house; Padre speaks about cows, cow’s dung, and urine. Astrologer speaks about cow and its dung but when Padre says, “I want to know why some of your people will not touch some other. You say cow dung and urine are holy, but even the shadows of some men are impure. How can that be?” (Sail 36). He defended that cow is holy and its dung and urine is a holy and thirty-three crore deities reside within her belly. Padre asked, “Doesn’t man bear the essence of the gods, too?” “Not all men. Just Brahmins. They emerged from Lord Brahman’s brain. The other castes emerged from his hands, his legs and his belly!” ‘Brahmins should have some extra faculties, then’

‘They do’

‘What is that?’

‘Intelligence.’

‘Others have that too!’

‘No, that’s the sort of intelligence oxen has” (Sail 37). Padre was so silent but when he was at St. Paul’s college, he read that “The Hindu epic Ramayana was written by Valmiki, a lowly Shudra, and the Mahabharata by Vyasa, a low

caste man whose mother sold fish. And the Bhagvad Gita was narrated by Krishna a Kshatriya on the battlefield” (Sail 39). When Padre speaks Astrologer was so angry, he replied, “Wrong! All wrong! The Ramayana and the Mahabharata were not written by one man, in one day. Hundreds of intellectual composed these books which kept growing for thousands of years” (Sail37). The society was practising a Sati System, especially the Nayaka community.

Age of Frenzy depicts forced conversion, the cruelty of the Portuguese, destruction of the Hindu temple and of Hindu culture. The Portuguese destroyed the Chamundeshwari temple at Chornem, they stopped Ratajatra. Portuguese passed the cruel order that, “Those who farm the temple’s land can continue doing so if they become Christians but all farm land and orchards owned by Hindus will be confiscated by the State” (Sail 42). The Portuguese destroyed the culture of Hindus and collapsed the economic condition of Indians. They threatened the Hindus, they said, “Become Christians, Or give the land to the Church” Or “Convert at once or we’ll take the harvest away” (Sail 47). There was a tragic story of Vitha. Shambhu is a brother of Vitha, when Shambu visits her house. She narrates the tragic story of the conversion. Her whole family members were converted to Christianity because of their economic condition. Vitha painfully requests Shambhu, “Just want to say one more thing don’t get trapped into anything, don’t stay back clinging to your field and orchards. If necessary, uproot yourselves and go far away. Don’t do what we have done” (Sail 48). Shambhu has remained silent. One of the elderly women asked Vithal, “So your brother came in the night, Vithai! Where did he eat? Where did he sleep? Did he drink water in your house?” Vithal replied, “No. He stayed hungry. Slept outside the house” “So what if he’s your brother? He’s outside now, of a different faith. Why make him sit on the porch? You should have sent him to our house” (Sail 51). Vithai did not speak anything.

Age of Frenzy depicts cruelty and conversion. Manju Nayak was converted to Christianity. Day by day Portuguese were so cruel that anyone who went against the tenets of Christianity was sentenced to death. The Portuguese army was cruel and the first thing, they did after setting foot in Goa was the massacre six thousand Moors. Portuguese took the wealth and property and took the widows and young women into their fields. Captain Diego Barrett Shef Camil Ribeir and his group entered a village. The soldiers had converted the Ramanath temple into a camp. They defiled the temple; Demu Guruv screamed “Don’t defile the shrine and the temple pond like this” (Sail 65). The captain glared at them, and then he drew his gun and pointed it at some monkeys on a nearby tree. He shoots the monkey and it fell. A group of unknown Chandals has entered the Betaal Shrine and defiled the temple. The villages had gathered to discuss about religion, and the captain said, “The King of Portugal is your ruler. His God is your God. His religion is your religion. All his subjects must become Christians” (Sail 71). The government was so cruel, they ordered “Anyone who practices another religion will be regarded as a traitor and expelled from his religion. We will build a church here” (Sail 72). Ghana Shena opposed the conversion, “We won’t become Christians” Captain speaks cruelly, “If you don’t convert of your own will, we’ll have to use force. Become Christians or leave the village” (Sail 72). He walked along with the soldiers.

Age of Frenzy depicts the true history of the conversion. Portuguese converted the Hindus by force or put fear and sometimes threats to convert. Sukhdev Nayak lived in Shivaddo, he was living alone in the dark and two of his sons sat in the courtyard and they asked him, he replied, “They have taken away the fertile fields that belonged to

the village Council. They will give those fields to those who convert to their faith” (Sail 82). They have been discussing conversion, and finally, they have decided to convert. Sukhdo Nayak met Padre, he introduced himself, ‘I am Sukdo Nayak. These are my sons. We’ve come to join your religion,’ “Do all of you want to become Christians?” “Yes”.

Padre Colaso was so happy, he expresses, “We will make the whole village Christian soon” (Sail 83-84). Sukhdo was silent, Padre Colaso said, “You will be baptized at St’ Lawrence’s Church next Sunday. Be here at daybreak. You’ll be given white garments and each of you will get four cruzados too” (Sail 83). Sukhdo’s wife did not convert. On the day of baptizm, the married women were asked to remove the beaded galsari from their necks and wipe the kumkuma from their foreheads. Padre gave a Christian name after they convert to Christianity, “Sukhdo Nayak become Salvador Dias, Molu Nayak become Manuel Dias, Ramkushta Nayak become Pedro Dias, Vasu Nayak became Jose Dias, Gopika wife of Molu Nayak became Isbel, Parvati become Fatima. Each of new converts received four cruzados coins. Gopika is the wife of Sukhdo Nayak, she opposed the conversion, “I’m not setting foot in there, and I’ll go somewhere and kill myself.’ The younger daughter-in-law, Parvati, laid a hand on her shoulder, “Akka, let’s go. We can’t change what’s in our fate sister!’ ‘What fate are you talking about? They’ve returned you into a widow even while your husband is alive, but what does that matter? All you care for is the money! Gopika snarled” (Sail 90). Padre Paulo Colazo blessed Sukhdo Nayak. Gopika said to her younger son, “Vasu, my son, I’d hoped that you would cook for me when I fell ill, but they’ve made a Christian of you too. You can’t even cremate me when I am dead. I will go to Pandharpur for the festival and threw myself into the Chandrabhaga River” (Sail 92). Sukhdar son uprooted tulsi plant in front of the house. A priest enters the house and was chanting a Latin prayer and sprinkled holy water and blessed the house. Guna Nayak and his two friends Raya and Shabi were good friends. There was a practice of untouchability in Goan society, when Guna opposed to convert to Christianity, the Portuguese government sent police to arrest Guna. But Guna escapes from his house, a group of soldiers came to search Guna. Constable Remet Noronha and six soldiers set off for Guna’s house. Guna’s parents and his younger brother emerged from the house, constable asked, “Where’s Guna?” “He has gone to the forest.” (Sail 102). Constable directed two of his men to enter the house, they wailed, “Deva! There Christians will pollute our house. We will be ruined. We’ll become outcastes” (Sail 102). Ravlu Nayak was stable; he asked him “Are you Hindu?” “Chaddo caste”. Constable orders him to check Guna inside the house, he replied, “They’re my enemies. How can I enter their house” “Just go in. They won’t mind an enemy setting foot in their house, but they don’t want a Christian in there. A slimy, poisonous snake will into make their house impure but a low caste Mahar will. They’ll sprinkle dung water seventeen times to purify the place. Ignorant, ungrateful people! Go, look in every corner and if you dare to lie, I will beat you to death!” (Sail 102). Guna’s wife Devki set her younger brother-in-law Mhadu to stop him from coming home. Guna and his wife have decided to leave the village, Guna destroyed the emblem of Christianity in the village and he disappeared into the darkness.

Age of Frenzy depicts the history of conversion and the principles of Christianity. Padre Simao continues his business of conversion. Dugga Mhar’s son Ghung converts. The government donates the Council’s field to those who convert to Christianity. Things have changed a lot; no one can raise their voice against a Christian in Goa. The

Solankhes family only practises Sati system in the village. Padre Simao speaks about Jesus's principles, "Love, compassion, and forgiveness are the main tenets of the Bible" (Sail 118). Those who have converted to Christianity practice Christianity and seek to go back to their old faith. There was ill-treatment and inequality in the faith of Christianity. Padre Colaso had lodged a complaint against Padre Simao. Three soldiers came and arrested Padre, they reached Gopattanam. Padre express, "My crime is just this, which I interpreted the teaching of the Bible in the right way, I understood what Jesus wanted to say and I tried to win men's hearts through love" (Sail 122). He confesses his crime before Inquisition Committee. The Hindus demolish the cross; the soldiers found seven culprits. Shef Riber and the soldiers got to Shirvaddo. Shef Riber sat down for a while, he summoned the elders and said, "See, this is a heinous crime. If the King of Portugal hears of this, he will send a force to destroy you. But the king stands by the solemn word he has given the people of Goa. If all of you become Christians, this crime will be forgiven. If you want to save your lives, you better convert at once" (Sali 124). Shabi, Raza and Guna were thinking to leave the village. Guna said, "They want us to become Christians. Everything will be forgiven, they say. Otherwise, they will kill us and set fire to our home. What do you say, shall we become Christians?" (Sail 124). They were not ready to convert but they are willing to die. Shef Riber said that The King of Portugal, the Viceroy and the kingship have declared that, "Hindus must not perform any rituals or worship idols in Goa. Idols are worshiped and religious ceremonies are performed in this temple. All of this must stop" (Sail 135). Bhatto and other of the villagers were thinking to convert to Christianity. Everyone was stunned. Nilu Nayak and other good friends decided to leave Goa. The Hindus were thinking about their own God. Bhadra Shenai retorted, "Our religion does not claim that God is manifested in just one form. We see God in animals. In fire and in water. In everything that exists. This entire universe and everything in it are a manifestation of the divine. Which is why we have thirty-three crore gods" (Sail 158). One day, the priest caught and he was furious, he scolds, "You are primitive uncivilized race. We have strength. We have guns and swords. We have Jesus and his love. If you do not become Christians peacefully, we shall use force or drive you out" (Sail 139). The King wants to convert everyone in this territory. Mahabaleshwar Sail depicts the truth of Nayak Community. The Nayaks of Shivaddo belonged to the warrior caste but there was nothing particularly brave about them. They could not mount an attack; they didn't support Guna when he protested against the atrocities.

There was a practice of prostitution in the Goa state, Aprupe was a prostitute, she was short, fair with a good figure but people called her Apu, "Her amber eyes were framed by thick, dark lashes" (Sail 145). She had been symbolically married to a peepal tree and wore the black beads in its name, like a married woman. Apu's mother was a woman of experience, who had entertained men in her youth. She said, "We are prostitutes, who serve this village. Whoever stops by for a night is treated as a husband. We cannot refuse anyone" (Sail 147). The numbers of people get pleasure from her.

Padre Colaso came and scolds villagers and forced them to convert to Christianity. The cruelty and harassment would continue in the Goa state. Padre Paulo Colaso was cruel and dangerous. He knows that if they control Brahmins, they could easily control the Hindus. Ramanath was the gramdev, the chief village deity, and the Kuldev of Nayak and Gurav communities. The Brahmin families were worshiped in the shrine at Rajgali. They did not practise the rituals and sacrifices to the lesser gods and spirits. Shef Riber came to the village and he wants to

ruin the Brahmins and destroy their influence. All the Brahmins assembled in the pathashala and the women and the women folk handled outside the door. They discussed the social issues, Rundra Shenai was so silent. The government has given time till the Shigmo festival, after that they want to destroy the temple. They have decided to remove their idol from the Shrine. Rudra Shenai's wife Sumitra keeps herself busy with fasts and rituals all through the year. Sumitra is ready to die but not convert to Christianity.

Age of Frenzy depicts the cruelty of the Portuguese in Goa state. Shef Camli Riber along with soldiers has camped and explained the law in detail. Ranu Kenkre was a tall fair man with a thick mustache on his round face. He is not ready to convert but Shef said, "You'll have to follow the law then. The viceroy is sending a strong message to Hindu convert to Christianity or leave Goa!" (Sail 166). Ranu Kenkre was intelligent and well educated; he was hurt by Colaso's accession. He explained Hindu Philosophy, "Hinduism and Christianity teach the same principles, this very little difference between the two. You go down on your knees before the statue of Jesus, Mother Mary and other Saints. We worship idols of our Gods. We believe that body and the soul are separate entities, that the soul is immortal and imbued with divine grace, just like you do. Good deeds take man to heaven and bad deeds lead to hell. We believe this too. There is just one difference. Our religion does not pardon us when we commit sins so each man has to suffer the fruits of his evil actions" (Sail 169). He refers to Padre Simao Peres; Colaso was irritated by the reference of Simao Peres. The Portuguese had destroyed the Lord Mangesh temple; no one knew whether the idol had been saved or whether it too had been destroyed. Bhadra, Rudra and Sabra Shena packed their belongings, they disordered the form implements and set the cattle loose. They want to take their god to a safe place; they crossed the river and went out of Goa and it become very dangerous in those days. They request a boatman; he helped them to cross the river. Durga's was the only Hindu family left in Raigali; it was only her field that remained fallow with no sign of activity. The Government used good techniques to suppress landowners, they put a heavy tax on them otherwise they have to convert or go to jail. By force Rana Kenkre converted to Christianity, Rana Kenkere now knows an Ikurik Kaisure, Ranu went to Durga's house and gave a small bag, he said, "There are forty xerafins in this. You should be able to reach Honnavar in Canara with this money" (Sail 181). Durga took the money and left.

Age of Frenzy depicts the culture of the Hindus in Goa. The people of that region had great faith in God Ravanath and would often visit the temple in Adolshi to seek his blessings. There was a festival meeting to discuss the arrangements for the festival. Everyone knows that this would probably be the last time, they would celebrate the festival. A huge crowd gathered in front of the temple when it was time to draw the chariot, Ventu Nayak broke five coconuts to mark the five settlements that made up Adolshi village. Ventu Nayak raised his hand and the chariot trundled and crowd cries of 'Har Har Mahadev!'. The rituals were done and it was time for the chariot to return to the temple. The Shigmo festival drew near the tension in the village began to mount. Jana Nayak, Mungru Shenai, and Demu Gurav were converted. Nilu Nayak said, "The idol of Lord Ramanth has been removed from the temple by the third day after the full moon. We will give our support to any brave man who will take the deity out of Goa" (Sail 190). Jana Nayak was furious; Ventu Nayak could not control his agitation. Demu Gurav (Dominic Soz) is not willing to do anything, he said, "I have lost everything I am a murderer. Killed my son because of my faith. Now I

have nothing, no son, and no religion. Do whatever you want” (Sail 190). Nilu Nayak finally took Mhablu’s seventeen-year-old son Shamblu. They set off to pick up the ceremonial sword from its shrine.

Age of Frenzy depicts the cruelty of the Portuguese who destroyed the Hindu temple without mercy. Captain Baruett came along with soldiers; Captain discussed issues with Shef Ribeir and Padre Colaso. People gather in small groups and discuss the development. Rayanna Bhat was watching the development. Rayanna went up and the Captian asked “You are the rulers why have taken over this land, why do you destroy the gods and the temple? Our faith is built around this deity and it is on Him that we depend for living” (Sail 211). Captain scolds him, “You served the temple all these years, serve the church from now on. We will build a large church here; we need people to work in it” (Sail 211). A few members of the Nayak community began to protest, but the officers would not care. They destroyed the temple, at the end of the day; the workers and soldiers bathed in the temple pool and drank there a large pot of liquor. They have completely destroyed the temple. They had even dug out the foundation stones and piled them up in a heap. The villagers lit oil lamps furtively as evening fell and prayed to their gods in low voice. Villagers were bathed in holy water and cleansed of all that was old when they were baptized and made Christians but, in their minds, and in their behaviour, Hinduism remained. Married women continued to wear the symbols of their status like the Hindus.

Age of Frenzy depicts the religious conditions of the Hindus during the Portuguese time. There was a critical situation for Hindus, many Hindus were in dilemma to convert to Christianity or remain as a Hindus. The Portuguese destroyed the Hindu temples without humanity, they feel themselves their religion is superior and they treat the Hindu religion negatively. Nilu Nayak is around sixty years old, Mhablu Nayak and Murari Nayak and their families were taking their God out of Adolshi. Nilu Nayak marched at the head of the group, the sword firmly in his grasp. Murari seventeen-year-old son followed and carried Lord Ramanath on his head. They had set out Antruz but when they came to the pilar embankment, they saw a man. He asked, ‘Who are you? From which village? Where are you headed?’ Nilu Nayak replied, “We’re from Adolshi, a rich flourishing village, struck now by the evil eye. We’re taking our gods with us. We will drive a stake into the ground and set up new homes at some favorable spot; our gods will be with us” (Sail 225). He suggested not going to that place, it is a dangerous place. It is an Island, it is full of Moors and Muslims and people from eighteen different communities. They stopped and cooked rice, after lunch, they picked up their gods and set off in the directions of the river Agashe. Nilu Nayak was familiar with the region; he had some idea and which direction people who were trying to escape conversion were headed. The boatmen and fishermen helped many people in the part; they took them as far as Shinvesor, Canara and Malabar. Nilu Nayak and his group reached Isorshi village which lay in the midst of the thick forest. They stayed in Nayak community house. The next day they started the journey. The novelist portrays the sentiments and feelings of the Goa people when they were traveling to another place. The sails were unfurled and the boat left the land, “Everyone was silent. Even the children seemed overword by the situation. Suddenly, Murari’s wife Kashi burst into tears. Mhablu’s wife Dulu stared at her with tears in her own eyes. Murari’s eyes were wet too” (Sali 229). Nilu realized that everyone on the boat was on the verge of tears. He did not know what to say them. He was taking them to some unknown land but he has planned to return home. They get off at the old beach and walk along the shore to a nearby village where they would find Konkani people from the Nayak community. They reached Kolamba village, it was a cool, shady region.

Age of Frenzy depicts the role of spirit; the spirit is a very important god in the Goa region. When Nilu Nayak reached Kolamba, Nayak of Adolshi requested permission to settle in the parts. Villagers strongly believed in the spirit they replied, “We take no step without consulting our gods. Lord Veerpurus is a powerful deity” (Sail 232). That night the spirit of the deity entered the body of Soyru, the temple jalmi. Villagers asked, “Strangers from some unknown regions want to settle here. What do you say?”

The spirit declared “Who are they? What caste? What is the bloodline that they have descended from? Without all the answers, they may not stay”.

Nilu said, ‘We’re Nayaks from Adolshi!’

‘Where’s the proof?’

‘Our tongue speaks the truth. That’s our only proof’

‘Not enough when they laid the foundation of your village temple, the identification stone was buried on the right side. There are five metal coins under the stone. Fetch them. One of those coins will trace your ancestry’

‘We can’t do that, deva.’ Mhablu said, ‘They’ve destroyed the temple and forced us to flee.’

‘Who is the deity that you bring?’

‘Our Gramdev. Lord Ramanath’

‘You will have to set up a new village for your gramdev. You can worship two Kuldevs in one village, but not two gramdevs. That will lead to violence and bloodshed!’ (Sail 232-233). Soyru came to normal; the Marashi sprinkled water on him and broke a coconut at his feet. Everyone was quiet, but the villagers seemed satisfied by what the spirit had decreed. Nilu Nayak realized the fact that he set off the next morning for Pansul village. But villagers stopped them; they did not permit them to stay along with their God. They left Kolamba and reached Shinvesar village. The village head permitted them to take rest, he asked, ‘Who’s your family deity?’

‘Lord Ramanath.’

‘And your village deity?’

‘Lord Ramanath’

‘Toss your gods into some lake and come with me then’ (Sail 236). Villagers would not agree, they would not permit them to stay with their gods. They picked up their belongings and followed Majala silently. The sunlight had mellowed by the time they walked down the slopes of the Pavsas Ghat and reached Majala. Nilu Nayak requested the villager to participate in village festival. Naga Bhat turned to the families from Adolshi, he said, “Ramanath is an incarnation of Ishwar and belongs to the Saiva tradition. He is represented by the black stone pindi or linga. Have you brought that with you? The Ramanath idol without the linga is like a man devoid of masculinity” Nilu Nayaka said, “No, we could not carry it. We left it behind. Those wretches must have destroyed it by now” (Sail 237). Nilu’s eyes filled with tears, Mhablu said, “We thought our gods were very powerful, the temple in our village was the best. But now we have neither village nor temple. Just this idol without the linga” (Sail 237). He declared, “We’ll stay here. We’ll do what you want” (Sail 237). Nilu had felt feverish and he passed away that night and his kinsmen cremated him under an Onvli tree on the beach. Naga Bhat performed the funeral rites.

There were lot of changes in the village Adolshi, Sukhdo and his sons-built ridges around the field. Jana Nayak lodge complaint against Sukhdo to Padre, "My neighbor, Sukhdo is going against our new religion. He clings to the old faith even today. He offers food to the crows and to cows and sends rice to the bhat's house to appease the spirits of his ancestors" (Sail 241). Padre Colas asked, 'Did you see Sukhdo Nayak perform their Hindu rituals?' 'Yes' Father" (Sail 241). Padre advised Jana Nayak to complain to the Inquisition officers. The Portuguese offered to treat slaves very badly. There was a big market of human sales; Branco had brought a fifteen-year-old girl Gorretti at the Lilao market. The old women at the marketplace had struck a finger into the girl's vagina to certify that she was a virgin. Branco's wife told the old Negress to send Gorretti to Anton's bed. Branco got Gorretti baptized in the church, the old Negress pushed Gorretti into Braco's son's bed room. One day because she draws water from the well, she met Gorey and he fell in love with her. There was a big punishment to slouch, "Everyone kept watch and if a man slave and a woman slave got into a relationship, they could be put to death" (Sail 245). A fine day came Gorretti and Gorey were disappeared.

Age of Frenzy depicts the Hindu culture and conversation in Goa state. Rudra Shenai returned to the village with his two younger sons, four months after they had left it. His wife passed away, they left the village hoping to protect their gods and their faith. When Devraj Shenai asked about Sumitra, Rudra's eyes are welled with tears and he narrates his tragic story. When they were traveling to a new place, some travellers came and picked up Rudra's Gods. Then he decided to go back to his village. The Inquisitor Officer enquired about the case of Padre Simao Peres. Padre Alex Dias Falcao was the chief inquisitor, he asked, "Do you know the changes you face and the reason you have been thrown into prison? 'No', 'You have spoken disrespectfully about the Holy Cross, the sacred emblem of Christianity. You have said that the cross on the hill was merely a stone structure, that there was nothing sacred about it. You condoned that vile act. We have examined the witness who testified against you" (Sail 271). Simao Peres believed in Jesus but did not bother to reply. He rang the silver bell violently and ordered the guards to take Simao away. There was a big torture of the prisoners in Goa during the Portuguese government. There was a special confession room, in which prisoners were tortured and forced to confess. They summoned him to the Holy assembly on the third day, the priest was weak and listless, and the light had gone out of his eyes. He Sank to his knees and made the sign of the cross before taking his place on the bench. The Chief Inquisitor asked:

'Do you confess to your crime against your religion?

Simao Peres nodded his head but the Inquisitor told him to speak up.

'Do you confess to all the Crime?'

'Yes'

'Did you commit these crimes consciously?'

'Yes'

'Do you make this confession of your own free will?'

'Yes'

'Describe the crimes you have committed against Christianity''.

'I believed in Christianity in the early years. I do so, today.

My faith wavered in between.'

‘Describe the crimes you have committed against Christianity’

‘I said it was merely a stone structure and not something divine’.

‘Do you regret your actions?’

‘Yes’.

‘Do you beg pardon for your sins? Do you swear that you will be a good Christian henceforth?’

‘Yes’ (Sail 279-280). On the Day of Judgment, the committee was declared that guilty of acting against the Christian religion. The Chief Inquisitor pronounced the sentence, “You are guilty so we condemn you to death by burning on the Day of Judgment. This is the punishment for your crime” (Sail 282). The Chief Inquisitor spark the silver bell, Simao Peres started at it intently as through guard appeared in the doorway and led him away. The priest woke up at four in the morning when it was still dark, Simao Peres stared at the two men, he read the names. One of them was Sukhdo Salvador Dias, his name seemed familiar. Sukhdo Nayak of Shirvadd, he was the first to convert to the Christianity along with three sons. Before the conversion, there was strict hierarchical patter but now everyone is equal. There was a fight between new convert who were originally Brahmins. They continued to mark the old castes before their new Christian names. They had become Christians but they could not get rid of their caste. The newly converted Christian was in confusion; they could not understand language and culture. There were three little shrines housing the deities. Agyo, Barmo and Vagro were at the edge of the village, beyond which was the thick forest. The villagers had a lot of faith in the powers of these deities and took care to ensure that they were not disturbed. The converted Christians continued the old tradition, like the traditional rituals, sacrificed the cock at the Vagro shrine offered the Sannas to Agyo and also placed the Choru and rent in front Barmo as offerings. The boatman was making a lot of money, these days taking people across the river as they moved out of Goa for various reasons. Bamu Gurav watched all this in silence, his face and eyes seemed carved in stone. That night he hanged himself from a tree in the forest because her brother had destroyed the temple he had built. The novel concludes that there was a big problem, there was no cross on the door but practising untouchability was still alive.

Work Cited

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